

THEORY OF EDUCATIONAL PSYCHOLOGY DURING PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract

Looking at the development of humanity and the social system it has passed through, we witness that the development of the individual is inextricably linked with the social society. The development of a person in space is expressed by the change and development of social relations, historical stages and periods. This article is devoted to the prohibition of innovations in the fields of pedagogy and psychology.

Key words: Educational process, teacher, educational place, pedagogical process, psychological service, success;

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The effectiveness of the educational process largely depends on the instructions given by the teacher. The role of the teacher is that he should create the rules for the students, what should be remembered temporarily, what should be remembered for life, what should be understood without completely remembering, what should be remembered verbatim, he should show the need to remember in order to tell the meaning in his own words. Observations show that when such instructions are not given, students often develop misconceptions.

Research methodology

Experiments show that students remember emotional material better than non-emotional material. The teacher should take care of the emotional side of the learning process. This problem is very important. Because, first of all, the content of education has become extremely complicated, and its size has increased tremendously. In order to achieve its successful mastering, it is necessary to strengthen the educational activities of students. Positive emotions have a strong impact on the effectiveness of academic work.

A dispassionate discussion done with frustration will appear, debated, and a work that is negatively treated with indifference will not be disappointed. The educational institution should create a creative attitude to the educational work in the students, and help the work to become a real creativity and a source of joy.

Analysis and results

It is known that two types of interest in psychology are defined in the educational process of students. The first is direct interest and the second is indirect interest. Every teacher tries to instill in his students an indirect interest in his subject. Through interests, students show an active attitude to education. In psychology, interest is a person's attitude toward certain things or events that are valuable or enjoyable to him. Interests are one of the important and individual characteristics of a person. Interests play a big role in students' lives. They are the main motivations that activate educational activities. Interests allow the students of educational institutions to learn the basics of science more correctly, to develop mental abilities, and to expand the scope of knowledge. The task of the teachers is not to force the student to engage in the work that he was initially interested in, but to deepen and expand his interests, to make them impressive, to turn them into a desire to engage in the activity that has become the center of interest.

The willingness of students to work towards a specific goal, to overcome difficulties, to refrain from distractions, and to develop a passion for learning is of particular importance in the educational process.

Conclusions

Thus, the subject of educational psychology is the facts, mechanisms and laws of the development of socio-cultural experience by a person, the laws of intellectual and personal development of a child as a subject of educational activities organized and controlled by a teacher. different conditions of the educational process (IAZimnyaya).

The subject of the science of pedagogy is to study the essence of the formation and development of the human personality and, on this basis, to develop the theory and methodology of education as a specially organized pedagogical process.

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